

Development of a Thermal and Electrical Conductive Composite Material with a Polymeric Matrix

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ABSTRACT

Short-fibre reinforced polymers are used in more and more fields of application in the present technology. They have excellent mechanical properties, combined with low density and the possibility to produce geometrical complex component parts in an injection molding process. Untill now the disadvantage of these composite materials was their low thermal conductivity. The new developed composite with aluminium alloy fibres has a high thermal conductivity, so that it can be used in structural parts where it is necessary to lead off the heat off boosters. The influences of the metallic fibres on the composite properties are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The field of application of the composite materials becomes greater and more important in the present technology. They substitute the traditional materials, like aluminum alloys. Thereby a reduction of the weight will be rendered with a high level of strength and stiffness. The reduction of the weight plays an important part in the aeronautical industry, through the possibility of increasing the power and or decreasing the fuel consumption of an aircraft.

Composite materials used in these field of application - mainly produced by the use of prepregs - apply in structural parts and skin component parts of an aircraft. Examples therefore are the wingtips of the "DO 328" and the fin of the "Airbus A310". In contrast to this most casing parts like fans pumps and so on are made by the use of light metal alloys. The materials used for these component parts have to accomplish further applications than materials used for structural parts. These are the electromagnetic shielding and the thermal conductivity, which is required to lead off the heat of the boosters.

A number of studies have been reported in the literature concerning the electrical conductivity of polymeric composite materials. The various researchers mainly have considered the influence of fillers and the coating of fibres on the electromagnetic shielding [1 - 4]. Only a few investigations were engaged in thermal conductivity of composites with polymeric matrix [4,5].

The reason described above leads to the development of a carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite, which can be used in an injection molding process. Beside the carbon fibres, which guarantee the strength and stiffness of the material, metallic particles in the matrix render the thermal an electric conductivity.

EXPERIMENTS

The investigations can be divided in two sections. In a first step (pre-investigations) the influence of the geometric shape and of metallic filler volume content on the thermal conductivity and the mechanical values were investigated. The samples for this investigations had a duroplastic matrix and were manufactured in a vacuum casting process. With the aid of the results determined in the pre-investigations, in a second step the investigations were carried out with samples manufactured in the injection molding process. The investigations were determined with samples with a thermoplastic matrix filled with metallic fibres.

Pre-Investigations

To investigate the influence of the geometric shape and the metallic filler volume content on the thermal and mechanical properties simple samples were manufactured in the vacuum casting process. With this manufacturing method the samples can be produced with low costs and in a short time. In order to get a high thermal conductivity and a low density of the composite it is necessary to use metallic fillers with high thermal conductivity and a low specific gravity. Therefore aluminium and aluminium alloys were used as the material of the metallic fillers. The geometric shapes of the fillers were powder, flakes and fibres. The material of the matrix was a duroplastic resin, especially used in the vacuum casting process.

The mechanical properties like tensile strength, tensile modulus and ultimate elongation were determined on a tensile testing machine. The thermal properties of the composites were investigated with a special measurement equipment to determine the thermal conductivity. The samples for this measurement had a length of 20 mm and a diameter of 6 mm.

Beside the traditional experimental investigations a new method was used to determine the thermal material properties. With the aid of the finite element method (FEM) and the simulation of the thermal behaviour in the microstructure of the composite, it was possible, to reduce the experimental investigations. The tri-dimensional models were generated with the FEM-Postprocessor *Patran*. The calculations were done with the software *P/Thermal* [6].

Experiments With Thermoplastic Matrix

The results from the pre-investigations show, that already low aluminium alloy fibre volume contents increase the thermal conductivity of the composite. Therefore, the composite material used for the further investigations was compounded from a thermoplastic resin and aluminium alloy fibres. The matrix was a semicrystalline polyaryletherketon, A1000, for high temperatures, produced by BASF. The fibres are made from the aluminium alloy AlMg 2.5. Before the compounding process they have a length of 3 mm and a diameter of about 30 μm . The properties of the matrix and fibres are given in Tabel 1. For the investigations two composites with fibre volume fractions of 10% and 22% were compounded. Investigations were carried out to determine the thermal conductivity, the mechanical properties and the debonding of the fibres during tensile load.

Table 1. Properties of matrix and fibre

Material	Tensile strength [MPa]	Tensile modulus [MPa]	Density [g/cm^3]	Thermal conductivity [W/mK]
Matrix A1000	104	4100	1.3	0.22
Fibres AlMg 2.5	210	70000	2.68	150

The thermal properties of the composite were investigated in two different ways. First, the thermal conductivity was measured by the same way as described (pre-investigations). In the

second method, hot water was pumped through a small tube, manufactured with the new composite material. The temperatures on the outside of the tube were measured at different points and then the thermal conductivity was calculated with the equation (1):

$$q = k * A/l * \delta T \tag{1}$$

Where q is the heat flux resulting from the temperature gradient δT and k is the thermal conductivity; A describes the cross-section area, l the wall thickness, in this case between 2 - 4 mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pre-investigations

Concerning the thermal conductivity, the results of the pre-investigations are illustrated in Fig. 1. The thermal conductivity of the composite material increases with an increasing content of metallic filler. Compared with Al-powder and Al-flakes filled composite, the composite filled with Al-fibres shows an high rise of the thermal conductivity with a low aluminium alloy fibre volume content.

Figure 1. Thermal conductivity of composites with different geometric shapes of the fillers

The results show, that the number of heat transfers between the matrix and the metallic filler has a great influence on the coefficient of the thermal conductivity. In a composite with very small particles there are a lot of heat transfers between the matrix and the filler. In a composite with long metallic fibres the numbers of heat transfers between the filler and the matrix are reduced. This leads to a high thermal conductivity in this kind of composite materials.

The results of the FEM-simulation confirm the results from the experiments. Fig. 2 shows a distribution of the temperatur in the microstructure of the composite. The temperature in the fibre is nearly constant. In front of and after a fiber there will be a large decrease of the temperature due to the low thermal conductivity of the matrix.

The investigations of the mechanical properties show the following results. The adhesion between the metallic fillers and the duroplastic resin is not sufficient to get a reinforcement of the composite. Fig. 3 shows the fracture surface of the Al-powder filled composite. The duroplastic resin has a brittle matrix fracture. The tensile load caused a debonding between the powder and the matrix.

Figure 2. Distribution of the temperature in the microstructure of the composite (FEM)
bright = high temperature, dark = low temperature

Figure 3. Fracture surface of an aluminium powder filled sample with duroplastic matrix

Fig. 4 shows the fracture surface of the AlMg 2.5-fibres filled composite material. The fracture surface of the sample shows a brittle matrix fracture. The cross-section of the fibres is not round but three-cornered. Due to the ductile fibre material a reduction of the cross-section area took place during the tensile testing. This led to a debonding and partially pull-out of the fibres. The fracture surface of the fibres shows dimples.

The poor adhesion between the duroplastic matrix and the metallic fillers caused no improvement of the mechanical properties of the composite materials.

Thermoplastic Matrix With AlMg 2.5-Fibres

The following section describes the results of the investigations with samples made of thermoplastic matrix. Two composite materials with different fibre volume contents have been investigated.

Figure 4. Fracture surface of an AlMg 2.5-fibre filled sample with duroplastic matrix

The results from the mechanical testing are shown in Fig. 5 and Table 2. The samples were tested under two different conditions. The "untreated" samples were tested after the injection molding process without a following heat treatment. The "treated" samples were tested after heat treatment at 300 °C during a period of 3 h. The heat treatment increases the crystallinity of the semicrystalline thermoplast.

The effect of the heat treatment is shown in Fig. 5. The tensile modulus of the "treated" samples is higher than the "untreated" samples. This is caused through a higher crystallinity of the matrix. The ultimate elongation decreases at higher fibre volume contents. The tensile strength of the composite material could not be improved by the addition of the aluminium alloy fibres.

Table 2. Properties of the Thermoplastic Composite

Fibre vol. %	Tensile strength [MPa]	Tensile modulus [MPa]	Ultimate elongation [%]
0	103	4100	4
10 untreated	87	5500	2.2
10 treated	91	6067	2.0
22 untreated	92	7300	1.7
22 treated	95	9242	1.5

The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of the mechanical testing. A sufficient improvement of the mechanical properties of the composite material can not be reached by the addition only of the AlMg 2.5-fibres. To get an improvement of the mechanical properties it is necessary to add carbon-fibres to the composite. The small influence of the metallic fibres on the mechanical properties can be explained by the consideration of tensile strength ratio and tensile modulus ratio of the fibre and the matrix (Table 3). An improvement of the mechanical properties of the composite material can only be achieved through the addition of fibres with a high tensile strength and modulus.

Figure 5. Effect of heat treatment on the tensile modulus of an AlMg 2.5-fibre filled composite

Table 3. Tensile Strength and Modulus Ratio

	Aluminium alloy fibre	Polymer	C-fibre
Tensile strength, [MPa]	210	103	3950
Ratio fibre/matrix		2	38
Tensile Modulus, [MPa]	70000	4100	238000
Ratio fibre/matrix		17	58

Fig. 6 shows the fracture surface of a sample. The thermoplastic semicrystalline matrix shows a brittle fracture. The ductile aluminium alloy of the fibres has a great reduction of the cross-section area and dimples on its fracture surface. On the surface of the fibres, a thin polymeric layer, which has a good adhesion on the fibre surface can be found. Investigations show, that the structure of this polymeric layer is amorphous. Due to the cross-section reduction of the fibres and due to the good adhesion of the polymeric layer at the fibre surface, the debonding took place between the semicrystalline matrix and the amorphous layer.

The crazings between the layer and the matrix confirm this assumption. The different structure of the polymer will be probably caused during the cooling of the composite. Due to the different thermal properties of the aluminium alloy and the polymer, the cooling rate around the aluminium alloy fibre will be higher than in the other matrix sections. The higher cooling rate causes a different crystallinity of the polymer around the fibre, which leads to an amorphous structure of the matrix.

The results of the thermal investigations at the 20 mm long samples are shown in Fig. 7. Compared with the results of the pre-investigations, the thermal conductivity rises with higher fibre volume contents. The investigations at the tubes, manufactured with the composite material led to higher thermal conductivities, with values of about 8 and 10 W/mK. This effect can be explained with the number of heat transfers in the composite material. At short distances there are only a few number of heat transfers between the aluminium alloy fibres and the polymeric matrix. In this case the characteristic of the composite due to the thermal conductivity is mainly influenced by the AlMg 2.5 fibres. At long distances the influence of the fibres decrease and the characteristic is mainly influenced by the thermal properties of the matrix.

Figure 6. Fracture surface of an aluminium alloy fibre filled sample with thermoplastic matrix

Figure 7. Effect of an increasing fibre content on the thermal conductivity and density

CONCLUSIONS

The investigations show, that a increase of the thermal conductivity can be reached only by the addition of the AlMg 2.5 fibres. Moreover it could be shown, that the thermal conductivity in such a composite material depends on the length of the heat conduction distance. The small length reduction of the aluminium alloy fibres during compounding and injection molding, compared with the carbon fibres, support the effect of the heat conduction in the composite. This has to be considered by the construction of the component parts.

Through the addition of the ductile aluminium alloy fibres a reinforcement of the matrix can not be achieved. To improve the mechanical properties of the composite, like tensile strength and tensile modulus it is necessary to add fibres to the matrix which have a high tensile strength and modulus, for example carbon fibres.

With the development of the new composite material it is now possible to produce geometrical complex component parts with in an injection molding process with a high thermal conductivity.

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